

BURST PRESSURE (HOOP TENSILE STRENGTH) OF COMPOSITE CYLINDERS USING ELASTOMERIC INSERTS

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• Pressure vessels:

• Applications:

- Filament winding:

Tailored strength and stiffness by adjusting the winding angle/pattern/number of layers.

- ↑ Automation
- ↑ Fiber positioning accuracy
- ↑ Fiber volume fraction
- ↓ Void content

• Testing:

Fluid-based pressurization

Stretching of a ring specimen

[1] Kim, W. T., & Kim, S. S. (2020). Design of a segment-type ring burst test device to evaluate the pressure resistance performance of composite pressure vessels. *Composite Structures*, 242.
 [2] Zhao, Y., *et al.* (2021). Split-disk test with 3D Digital Image Correlation strain measurement for filament wound composites. *Composite Structures*, 263.

OBJECTIVE

To assess the use of the compressed elastomer method for testing internal pressure of filament-wound cylinders/tubes

- **Specific objectives:**

- ✓ To assess the mechanical response of cylinders for different winding angles, including the hoop tensile strength (*burst pressure*) and modulus;
- ✓ To identify advantages and limitations of the method for testing FW cylinders and to provide recommendations for the testing of similar structures.

• Cylinder manufacturing

Carbon-epoxy towpregs

Kuka robot with MFTech system.
Stainless-steel mandrel Ø 50.8 mm,

Oven with air circulation for 45 min @140 °C

Length: 110 mm
5 specimens each for: ±35°, ± 45°, ± 55°, ± 75°, ± 90°

Material

Design

Winding

Curing

Sampling

CadWind® software

• Compressed elastomer test method [3]

Pushrods

SAE 1040

Silicone discs
(many)50 Shore A
3 mm thick

• Dimensioning [4]

$$\beta = \sqrt[4]{\frac{3(1-\nu^2)}{r_i^2 t^2}}$$

ν : Poisson's ratio (0.5)
 r_i : inner radius
 t : wall thickness

Pressurized length $\geq 9/\beta$

Unpressurized ends $\geq 3,5/\beta$

Talcum powder

[3] ASTM C1819-21 - Hoop Tensile Strength of Continuous Fiber-Reinforced Advanced Ceramic Composite Tubular Test Specimens at Ambient Temperature Using Elastomeric Inserts

[4] Mosley, K. (1982). The stressing for test purposes of materials in tubular form using elastomeric inserts — experimental and theoretical development. *Proc. of Inst. of Mechanical Engineers*, 196.

- Instron universal testing machine – 100 kN load cell.
- Displacement rate: 10 mm/min.

 $\pm 35^\circ$

• Load × displacement

Equivalent internal pressure:

$$p = \frac{F}{\pi r_i^2}$$

where: F is the axial load, r_i the inner radius of the cylinder.

- Typical fracture morphologies

 $\pm 35^\circ$

• Hoop stress × hoop strain

±35°

±45°

±55°

±75°

±90°

Hoop tensile stress:

$$\sigma_h = \eta_m p \frac{2 r_i^2}{(r_o^2 - r_i^2)}$$

where: η_m is the maximum stress factor [4], r_o the outer radius of the cylinder.

- Effective mechanical properties in the hoop direction

Effective modulus of elasticity (hoop direction):

$$E = \frac{\Delta\sigma_h}{\Delta\epsilon_h}$$

slope of the stress \times strain curve in the linear region (1000-2000 $\mu\text{m}/\text{m}$ or 500-1000 $\mu\text{m}/\text{m}$)

- **The compressed elastomer method enabled:**
 - Good load control.
 - Easy assembly/disassembly.
 - Reduced time and cost requirements.
 - Less critical problems in comparison to fluid pressurization testing (safety and seals).
 - Evaluation of tubes, as opposed to ring specimens.

- **Regarding the mechanical behavior of the FW cylinders:**
 - Greater load capacities for higher WA (up to 75° in relation to the cylinder axis).
 - 35° and 45° failed progressively, primarily by interlaminar mechanisms.
 - 55° failed by wall fracture in the pressurized region and 75° failed explosively.
 - ≈90° failed parallel to the fiber orientation due to axial bending loads at the non-pressurized ends.

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Thank you!

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